

Board Governance and Sustainability Disclosure in Nigeria Listed Deposit Money Banks

¹Onipe Adabenege Yahaya ²Idris Mohammed ³Shuaibu Garba Mohammed

^{1&3}Department of Accounting, Faculty of Management Sciences, Nigerian Defence
Academy, Kaduna, Kaduna State, Nigeria

²Department of Accounting, Faculty of Management Sciences, Kaduna State University,
Kaduna, Kaduna State, Nigeria

Citation: Yahaya, O. A., Mohammed, I., & Mohammed, S. G. (2022). Board governance and sustainability in Nigeria Listed Deposit Money Banks. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 10(5), 126-146.

ABSTRACT: *There is low disclosure of sustainability matters (environment, social, governance) among Nigerian banks. It is true the board plays significant part in ensuring disclosure (Global Reporting Initiatives, 2006). We look at how board governance affects sustainability reporting for 2012 through 2021. The sample was 13 because it was limited to deposit money banks. The study adopted correlational research design and the data were analyzed with the aid of multiple regression model based on Probit estimation. This study found board independence positive and significant, while board size, meeting, gender diversity, share ownership, and remuneration are insignificant. On the control variables, ownership concentration, debt and listing age are significant, while firms with the big4 auditors are insignificant. This is among the few studies to examine board governance and sustainability exposé. However, a discussion on the role of board governance is necessary. The paper calls for more studies on whether board governance determines sustainability disclosure. This conclusion is important for shareholders and regulators to appreciate that board size, the frequency of board meetings, women on the board, equity holdings by members of the board and their remuneration have no bearing on sustainability disclosure.*

KEYWORDS: *board of directors, board governance, sustainability disclosure, reporting, Nigeria*

INTRODUCTION

There is a growing interest in board governance (BG) and sustainability disclosure (SD). See (Githaigi & Kosgei, 2022; Herda et al., 2012; Mnif & Borgi, 2020; Nelson & Grayson, 2017; Umar et al. (2021), van Buskisk, 2012; Yahaya & Alkasim, 2021). As shown by Nwsimloo et al. (2020), a number of theories have been applied in research on the nexus link BG and SD, including Stakeholders' Theory, Agency Theory, Positive Accounting Theory and Predicting Accounting Theory. Past research in the BG-SD tie has modeled the relationship with little attention (Rezee, 2009). However, BG-SD is not implemented indiscriminately, as one stop solution. Instead, as suggested by Araissi et al. (2016), there is difference in what is

implementable and also in terms of impacts. Still, rather little attention is paid to the connection. This is a weakness of past research on the association between BG and SD. Empirical findings showing that there is considerable disparity in SD as it is implemented (Ahmed et al., 2018). Therefore, in this paper, the BG-SD relationship is presented as an alternative.

Over the years, financial regulatory bodies are concerned with corporations' attitude towards sustainability reporting. There is poor (low) form of environmental, social and governance disclosures in Nigeria. There is the need for frequent reports by the management. The Global Reporting Initiative (2006) has emphasized on the need to determine the extent at which corporate organizations impacted on the people, environment as well nation's economy through disclosure of comprehensive financial and non-financial information which inform the investors as well as other stakeholders about the responsibility and transparency as well as the legitimacy of the business operation. Sustainability reporting is basically aim at ensuring the accuracy and credibility of business operations, aside the business impact on governance, social, economic as well as environmental (Githaig & Kosgei, 2022). Similarly, the World Business Council for Sustainable Development as cited by Nelson and Grayson (2017) consider sustainability reporting as the companies public report which involve the corporate position on economic, environmental and social dimensions activities.

Board of directors are governing bodies of corporate organizations that are often seen to be responsible for formulating corporate policies and strategies of their businesses through effective plans based on the established objectives and the core value of an organization. Aside the formulation of corporate policies of an organization, board of directors are often seen to be responsible ensuring that a comprehensive periodic financial and none financial information to their various stakeholders about the general activities and wellbeing of the businesses through. That serves as a means of accessing the level of transparency and accountability of the management which may ultimately reduce information asymmetry between the management and stakeholders (Herda et al., 2012; van Buskirk, 2012). According to Mnif and Borgi (2020) and Nursimloo et al. (2020). The boards of directors are also seen to be responsible for ensuring a sustainability reporting disclosure in an organization.

Considering the importance of sustainability disclosure, a number of researches were conducted in different part of world particularly in relation to sustainability reporting such as Rezaee (2009), Araissi et al. (2016), Ahmad et al. (2018), Bektur and Arzova (2020), Buallay et al. (2020), Cicchiello et al. (2021) and Beji et al. (2021) among others. Moreover, similar studies were carried out in Nigerian context such as Enahoro (2009), Asaolu, et al (2011), Asuquo (2012), Ejoh et al. (2014), Dibia and Onwuchekwu (2015), Haladu and Salim (2016), Eberhardt-Toth (2017), Ndalun et al. (2021) and Chinonyelum and Ndubuisi (2022) among others. Yet, none of these studies focused on board characteristics in relation to sustainability reporting among listed DMBs in Nigeria.

Therefore, considering the significant role of listed deposit money banks (DMBs), we look board governance-SD nexus for 2012/2021 in order to fill the existing knowledge gap from the reviewed literatures. The paper considered board attributes represented by (board size, meetings, independence, female directors, equity holdings, remuneration) and sustainability reporting disclosure as dependent variable of listed DMBs in Nigeria.

The findings of this paper will serve as a basis for further study. Accordingly, the findings will serve as guide for decision making policies of the banks in Nigeria. The outcome of the study will further serve as vital information to all the relevant regulatory authorities such as Central Bank of Nigeria, Nigerian Securities and Exchange Commission, Nigerian Deposit Insurance Corporation, Federal Inland Revenue Service, among others. Other stakeholders may consider the outcome of the study useful for decision making. The paper consists of introduction, related literature, methodology, results and discussion, as well as conclusions and recommendations.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

This section is premised on literatures on board size, meeting (diligence), independence, board gender diversity, ownership-concentration, remuneration vis-a-vis SD. Board size means size of directors of a corporation. Board meeting refers to times that the board meets on behalf of the company. Board independence is interpreted to mean the fraction of non-executive directors in relation to size of the board. Board gender diversity refers to the proportion of women and board ownership refers to equity holdings of the members of the board. Board remuneration (incentives) implies financial compensations for holding the appointment.

Board size and SD

In terms of empirical studies, Uwuigbe et al. (2011) looked at 40 listed firms in Nigeria from 2006 to 2010 to see if there was a link between the size of the board and the level of corporate environmental disclosure, which is a subset of sustainability disclosure. The results showed that board size was strong and negative with how much environmental information a company shares. Oba and Fodio (2012) looked at how board characteristics affect 21 firms that are sensitive to the environment. They found an inverse relationship between board size and environmental reporting. Also, Jangu et al. (2014) looked at how good corporate governance (CG) affected the sustainability disclosure of 100 public companies in Malaysian market. The outcomes presented that board size has weight on sustainability disclosure. Also, Shamil et al. (2014) looked at the 2012 annual reports of 148 companies that were listed on the Colombo Stock Exchange (CSE) in Sri Lanka. They looked at how the characteristics of the board affected the sustainability reporting of those companies. This study found that the size of the board is related to sustainability reporting in a good way.

In 2013, Osazuwa et al. (2016) studied 116 organizations' board characteristics and environmental disclosures. They found that board size is linked to environmental disclosure in a positive way. Further, In Singapore, Hu and Loh (2018) looked into how board governance and sustainability disclosure are linked. When it comes to the size of the board, companies with bigger boards are more likely to report on sustainability, and the quality of their reports is better. Also, Mahmood et al. (2018) saw CG and economic, social, and environmental sustainability disclosures of one hundred companies in Pakistan for 2012-2015. This study came to the conclusion that a large board with a female director and a CSR committee (CSRC) is better able to check and control decisions about sustainability made by management. Aliyu (2018) looked into corporate governance and environmental reporting for 24 corporations from 2011 to 2015. There is no strong link between the size of the board and CER.

Khairredine et al. (2020) looked at corporate board and governance-environmental-ethics disclosures using eighty-two companies for 2012-2017. Only corporate environmental disclosure is linked to board size in a positive and significant way. Also, Agyemang et al. (2020) looked at board and environmental accounting information disclosure among Chinese organizations. They looked at 34 companies for 2000-2018. They established significantly positive correspondence concerning board size-environmental disclosure index. Kumari et al. (2022) looked at the effect of board characteristics (BC) on a company's environmental performance using from 2015-2020 data from the National Stock Exchange of India (NSE) 500 listed companies in India's environmentally sensitive and non-sensitive industries reported on 1,158 firm-year observations.. BS is linked to ED in a positive and significant way for both sensitive and non-sensitive industry groups.

H₀₁: Sustainability reporting is not significantly impacted by BS.

Board meetings and SD

Osazuwa et al. (2016) interrogated 116 Nigeria corporations and discovered that board meetings were bad for environmental disclosure and good for board meetings. In Singapore, Hu and Loh (2018) looked into how board governance and sustainability disclosure are linked. Companies with bigger board meetings are more likely to do sustainability reporting, and the quality of their reports is higher. Also, Aliyu (2018) looked into the link between corporate governance and environmental reporting for 24 organizations for 2011-2015. The study shows that there is a positive, significant link between board meetings and CER.

Khairredine et al. (2020) looked at board and disclosures for 2012/2017. Governance, environmental, and ethics disclosure are all improved by board meetings in a big way. Agyemang et al. (2020) looked at the board and environmental disclosure for companies in China. They looked at thirty-four companies. At the 1% significant level, board meetings were linked to EADI in a positive way. Oyekale et al. (2021) probed CG and ESD in seventy-two in nonfinancial corporations for 2012-2020. Board Meetings are negatively and insignificantly affect environmental sustainability disclosure. Kumari et al. (2022) looked at

the effect of the board on a company's environmental disclosure (ED). For both sensitive and non-sensitive industry groups, the number of meetings has a strong and positive link to ED.

H₀₂: Sustainability reporting is not significantly impacted by number of meetings.

Board independence and SD

Readings indicated that non-executive directors partake in business decisions made by the board, which makes sense given their important role in making policies and business decisions. So, some studies looked at how the independence of the board affects sustainability reporting in different parts of the world. For example, Gul and Leung (2004) found that the number of independent directors has a big and negative effect on the number of voluntary sustainability disclosures. Further, But Janggu et al. (2014) said that board independence and sustainability disclosure of 100 sampled Malaysian companies don't have a big effect on each other. Masud et al. (2018), on the other hand, looked at the effect of corporate governance on environmental sustainability reporting in 88 listed companies from certain South Asian countries from 2009 to 2016. They found non-executive directors good for environmental sustainability reporting. In a similar way, Ong and Djajadikerta (2018) looked at corporate mechanism and SD of 133 Australian resource industries in 2012. It was discovered that nonexecutive directors stand good for SD.

In the same way, Khaireddine et al. (2020) established positively-statistically significant relationship between board independence and sustainability disclosure among 82 sample firms from 2012 to 2017. Also, Gardazi et al. (2020) looked at the link between the board's characteristics and the energy industry in Malaysia's sustainability disclosure. It was found that there is a strong and positive link between board independence and disclosure about sustainability. Agyemang et al. (2020) observed the effect of board characteristics on environmental accounting information disclosure for listed mining companies in China. They looked at thirty-four mining corporations for 2000/2018. Board independence, as measured by independent directors, and the fact that the CEO is not also the board chairman showed that EADI has a good and important relationship with the company. Furthermore, Vitolla et al. (2020) looked into the link between board independence and sustainability reporting at 134 international companies. It was found that there is a strong link between board independence and the quality of sustainability reports. Following these divergence views, this paper asserts that:

H₀₂: Board independence has no significant effect on sustainability disclosure

Board gender diversity and SD

Studies have found a link concerning women on boards as a part of corporation governance and SD. In that regards, Ntim and Soobaroyen (2013) pointed out that having a mix of men and women on the board helps a company's legitimacy. This is one of the main reasons why sustainability reporting is important, as it helps strengthen relationships between different

stakeholders. This could be seen as diversity inclusion through sustainability reporting. But, Shamil et al. (2014) observed a strong and negative link connecting women and SD.

Amran et al. (2014) found that there is no significant link between the number of women on a board and a company's ability to stay in business. Fernandez-Feijoo et al. (2014) established that female board members have a significant and positive effect on sustainability reporting in 22 countries around the world. This is in line with the Global Gender Gap Report and the Women on Board's Report from 2011 and 2012, respectively. Shamil et al. (2014) investigated the influence of board characteristics on sustainability reporting of 148 listed companies in the Colombo Stock Exchange (CSE), Sri Lanka from the 2012 annual reports. This study documented female directors as negatively related to SD. Araissi et al. (2016) theorized that women board members encourage corporate social activities that are part of sustainability reporting in a normal business operation. Khan's study from 2010 found that there is no significant link between commercial banks in Bangladesh and the number of women on their boards when it comes to sustainability reporting.

Agyemang et al. (2020) looked at the effect of board characteristics on environmental accounting information disclosure for 34 listed mining companies in China from the Shanghai and Shenzhen Stock Exchanges between 2000 and 2018. In terms of diversity, the women on board showed that they had a negative and small relationship with environmental disclosure index. Buallay et al. (2020) said the number of women in boards affects the decision about how to keep the business going. So, there is a strong positive link between gender diversity and sustainability reporting. Similarly, Gardazi et al. (2020) said that there is a strong and positive link between gender on the board and sustainability disclosure. In another study, Chinonyelum and Ndubuisi (2022) looked at the effect of board structure on sustainability among industrial goods firms in Nigeria. They found that having a lot of women on the board has a big positive effect on sustainability reporting. In regards with these conflicting findings, the paper formulates the following null hypothesis:

H₀₄: Sustainability reporting is not significantly impacted by the presence of women on the board.

Board ownership and SD

Janggu et al. (2014) looked at the effect of good corporate governance (CG) on the sustainability disclosure of 100 public listed companies in Malaysia. Board ownership and independence did not play a big role in getting sustainability disclosure. Dienes et al. (2016) systematised the research field of sustainability reporting. The authors looked at the drivers of sustainability reporting. The review suggested that ownership structure is an important driver of the disclosure of sustainability reports. Masud et al. (2018) looked at CG and environmental sustainability reporting in Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan between 2009 and 2016. They used the sustainability reports of 88 listed organizations to do this. They found a strong link between director share ownership and ESRP. Between 2009 and 2016, Bae et al. (2018) looked at the link between corporate governance and total sustainability disclosure in

Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan. They found that director shareholding is linked to total sustainability disclosure in a way that is negative and significant.

Dewi et al. (2019) looked at managerial ownership and environmental disclosure at 117 corporations for 2015-2017. They found empirical evidence of this effect. The study's results showed that managerial ownership is good for environmental disclosure. Gerged (2020) used a sample of 500 firm-year observations in Jordan to assess CG-environmental disclosure. Based on the results of this study, it seems that managerial ownership and ownership concentration are linked to less environmental information being shared in Jordan. Amosh and Khatib (2021) looked at ownership structure-ESG disclosure in Jordan. They did this by looking at 51 annual reports of Jordanian industrial companies listed from 2012 to 2019. The results showed how bad it is for block holders to own shares and for managers to own shares. H₀₅: Sustainability reporting is not significantly impacted board ownership.

Board remuneration and SD

Haque (2017) used 256 non-financial UK firms over a 13-year period (2002–2014) to study the effects of board characteristics and sustainable compensation policy on carbon reduction initiatives and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions of a firm. ESG based payment plan is linked to carbon reduction efforts in a good way. Also, Al-Shaer and Zaman (2019) used a sample of UK FTSE350 companies from 2011 to 2015 to look at sustainability-related goals in CEO compensation contracts. The results showed the potential of assured sustainability reports.

Agyemang et al. (2020) looked at board-environmental information disclosure in China. They assessed thirty-four companies for 2000 to 2018. There was not a clear link between incentive (pay) characteristics and environmental disclosure index. Jaturat et al. (2021) looked into how the characteristics of the board of directors affect sustainability disclosures and how corporate governance acts as a middleman. The results of the study show that compensation motivation has an effect on how companies talk about sustainability. Oyekale et al. (2021) looked at CG-environmental SD in 72 nonfinancial corporations for 2012-2020. Remuneration Committee's effect on environmental sustainability disclosure is small but positive. Based on these contrasting results, the paper proposes that:

H₀₆: Board remuneration has no significant effect on sustainability disclosure.

We now focus on the control variables in this paper (big 4 auditors, ownership concentration, leverage/debt, and listing age of firm). Mock et al. (2009) looked at a sample of 130 entities from around the world that released assured sustainability reports between 2002 and 2004. In particular, they looked into the link concerning Big 4 and SD. Figures showed that big 4s issued over 50% SD. Also, Also, Perego (2009) looked into why 136 companies that wanted independent verification of their sustainability reports chose different assurance providers and what happened as a result. The paper showed that the big four accounting firms have a positive effect on the quality of assurance in terms of how reports are formatted and how assurance is done.

Herbohn et al. (2014) looked into the link between sustainability performance and sustainability disclosure in the Australian extractive industries. Using information from 339 mining and energy companies that were listed on the Australian Securities Exchange in 2006, it was found that age was related to sustainability in a positive way. Further, Gavana et al. (2017) looked at how 230 Italian firms felt about using sustainability reporting to make it easier to get money from outside sources. They said that companies are more likely to say when they plan to issue equity or bonds.

Alotaibi (2020) looked at 119 non-financial companies that were listed on the Saudi stock market between 2015 and 2017 to find out what made them tell the public about their environmental sustainability. The results of this paper showed that the age of a company is an important factor. Marwa et al. (2020) used a sample of 81 nonfinancial corporations quoted on the SBF 120 index for 2012-2017 to study the relationship between audit quality and environmental disclosure. They found a link between the level of voluntary disclosure of environmental information and the environmental auditor's BIG 4 and debt level that was statistically significant. Viana and Crisóstomo (2020) analyzed the effects of ownership concentration on the social and environmental disclosure of 1,252 annual observations of 252 companies from 2010 to 2014. The results showed that social and environmental disclosure by Brazilian companies is related to the number of votes they get. Kumari et al. (2021) looked at the sustainability disclosure practices of the 75 top listed nonbanking companies in India that were in the NIFTY100 Index from 2014-2015 to 2018-2019. Based on what has been seen in the real world, it seems that age has a positive relationship with how much information a company shares about its sustainability efforts. Contrary to what was expected, financial gearing has a negative effect on SD of companies in India.

After looking at both conceptual and empirical literatures, the stakeholders' theory was adopted for the paper. The theory recognizes that businesses have several stakeholders whose interests should be kept in a balance. The theory recognizes the interests of employees, managers, owners, the company itself, suppliers, society, customers, government, creditors and shareholders. It simply accounts for multiple constituencies to which the corporation's operations affect and is affected by them.

METHODOLOGY

Correlational design was used in the study to look at BG-SD nexus. Data came from secondary sources, specifically the audited financial statements of 13 publicly traded companies from 2012 to 2021. So, the study used a census sampling method to look at all the 13 banks. Githaiga and Kosgei's model from 2022 was changed to figure out the relationship between BG and SD. The panel model of the study is specified thus:

$$SUSTA_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BSIZE_{i,t} + \beta_2 BMEET_{i,t} + \beta_3 BINDE_{i,t} + \beta_4 BDIVE_{i,t} + \beta_5 BOWNE_{i,t} + \beta_6 BREMU_{i,t} + \beta_7 BIGFO_{i,t} + \beta_8 OWNEC_{i,t} + \beta_9 DETAS_{i,t} + \beta_{10} FLAGE_{i,t} + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

While:

SUSTA = Sustainability disclosure is measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to firm with annual reports with sustainability impact information and "0" for otherwise (Umar et al., 2018; Yahaya, 2021).

BSIZE = Board size measured as the total numbers of directors of a company (Agyemang et al., 2020; Khaireddine et al., 2020; Kumari et al., 2022; Yahaya & Apochi, 2022).

BMEET = Board meetings is the number of meetings held by the board in a year (Khaireddine & others, 2020; Kumari & others, 2022; Oyekale & others, 2021).

BINDE = Board independence is nonexecutive directors divided by board size (Khaireddine et al., 2020; Yahaya & Apochi, 2022)

BDIVE = Board gender diversity measured as the number of female directors divided by total board size (Agyemang et al., 2020; Buallay et al., 2020; Yahaya & Apochi)

BOWNE = Board share ownership is directors' holdings divided by total shares ((Dewi et al., 2019; Dienes et al., 2016).

BREMU = Board remuneration is directors' payment divided by sales (Agyemang et al., 2020; Jaturat et al., 2021; Oyekale et al., 2021).

BIGFO = Big 4 auditors measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that use PWC, Deloitte, E&Y and KPMG as external auditors and "0" otherwise (Perego, 2009).

OWNEC = Ownership concentration measured as the shares ownership concentration of all the block shareholders with 5% and above shares ownership (Viana & Crisóstomo, 2020).

DETAS = Debt to total assets measured as total liabilities divided by total asset (Gavana et al. (2017; Yahaya & Andow; Yahaya & Lamido, 2022)

FLAGE = Firm listing age measured as number of years a company is trading in the stock exchange (Alotaibi, 2020; Herbohn et al., 2014; Kumari et al., 2021).

β_0 = Intercept

β_{1-10} = Coefficient of the explanatory variable

i = Firms (13 firms)

t = Time (10 years)

ε = Error term

RESULTS

The results of the model are reported in Tables 1 to 10 and Figures 1 to 2 as indicated underneath:

Table 1
Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
SUSTA	130	.546	.5	0	1
BSIZE	130	13.438	3.446	5	21
BMEET	130	5.777	2.11	2	13
BINDE	130	60.575	11.754	36.842	90
BDIVE	130	16.808	10.667	0	60
BOWNE	130	9.908	14.621	0	71.597
BREMU	130	1.159	2.001	.009	11.463
BIGFO	130	.762	.428	0	1
OWNEC	130	28.869	25.48	0	89
DETAS	130	87.424	19.324	68.92	254.75
FLAGE	130	22.692	15.428	2	50

STATA Yields

As indicated in Table 1, observations total 130. Sustainability (SUSTA) averages .546 with a standard deviation of .5 and lowest and highest of 0 and 1. It is noted that the volatility of this variable is high when compared with its mean. Also, board size (BSIZE) averages 13 with a standard deviation of 3 members and lowest and highest of 5 and 21. The number of meetings (BMEET) of the board averages 6 with a standard deviation of 2 and lowest and highest of 2 and 13. Similarly, board independence (BINDE) averages 61% with a standard deviation of 12% and lowest and highest of 37% and 90%. Board gender diversity averages 17% with a standard deviation of 11% and lowest and highest of 0% and 60%. This means that there are firms without female director. Board ownership averages 10% with a standard deviation of 15% and lowest and highest of 0% and 72%, meaning that in some firms directors have zero stake. In terms of compensation, board remuneration averages 1.2% with a standard deviation of 2% and lowest and highest of 1% and 12%.

On the control variables, big4 (BIGFO) averages .762 with a standard deviation of .428 and lowest and highest of 0 and 1. In addition, ownership concentration (OWNEC) averages 29% with a standard deviation of 26% and lowest and highest of 0% and 89%, meaning that for some corporations, equity is not concentrated at all. Leverage (DETAS) averages 87% with a standard deviation of 19% and lowest and highest of 69% and 255%, suggesting that firms in Nigeria are highly geared. Finally, listing age averages 23 years with a standard deviation of 15 years and lowest and highest of 2 years and 50 years. Table 2 reports the results of correlation investigation.

Table 2

Pairwise correlations

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)
(1) SUSTA	1.000										
(2) BSIZE	-0.167 (0.057)	1.000									
(3) BMEET	-0.067 (0.447)	0.227* (0.009)	1.000								
(4) BINDE	0.434* (0.000)	-0.368* (0.000)	0.068 (0.443)	1.000							
(5) BDIVE	-0.065 (0.459)	0.050 (0.574)	0.021 (0.811)	-0.036 (0.684)	1.000						
(6) BOWNE	-0.058 (0.515)	-0.125 (0.156)	-0.079 (0.370)	-0.105 (0.237)	-0.163 (0.063)	1.000					
(7) BREMU	0.002 (0.979)	-0.371* (0.000)	-0.065 (0.463)	0.068 (0.439)	-0.127 (0.150)	0.087 (0.323)	1.000				
(8) BIGFO	0.215* (0.014)	-0.123 (0.163)	-0.283* (0.001)	0.071 (0.423)	-0.166 (0.060)	0.218* (0.013)	0.165 (0.061)	1.000			
(9) OWNEC	0.155 (0.077)	0.063 (0.479)	-0.382* (0.000)	-0.063 (0.480)	0.003 (0.973)	0.137 (0.120)	-0.076 (0.388)	0.368* (0.000)	1.000		
(10) DETAS	-0.155 (0.078)	-0.003 (0.976)	-0.087 (0.327)	-0.121 (0.169)	-0.061 (0.489)	0.036 (0.685)	-0.069 (0.436)	-0.237* (0.007)	0.086 (0.330)	1.000	
(11) FLAGE	0.085 (0.335)	0.142 (0.108)	0.091 (0.301)	-0.077 (0.384)	-0.168 (0.056)	0.035 (0.691)	-0.141 (0.110)	0.129 (0.145)	-0.128 (0.146)	0.056 (0.527)	1.000

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

STATA Yields

Table 2 results indicate that some of the variables in relation with sustainability are significant at 1% and 5%. None is significant at 10%. For example, only board independence and big4 auditors are positive and significant. Board size, meetings, diversity, share ownership, remuneration, ownership concentration, leverage and listing age are not significant. The results of ordinary least square are contained in Table 3 for the purpose of regression diagnostics. There is no need to interpret the results in Table 3 because they are only used for checking of residual, homoscedasticity, unusual and influential data, multicollinearity, linearity, model specification error and panel effects. Figure 1 shows the results of test of unusual and influential data.

Table 3

Linear regression

SUSTA	Coef.	St.Err.	t	p	[95% Cf Interval]	Sig
BSIZE	0	.011	0.01	.995	-.022 .022	
BMEET	0	.017	0.00	.996	-.034 .034	
BINDE	.013	.003	4.37	0	.007 .019	***
BDIVE	-.003	.003	-1.01	.316	-.009 .003	
BOWNE	-.003	.002	-1.24	.216	-.007 .002	
BREMU	-.022	.017	-1.26	.212	-.056 .013	
BIGFO	.09	.09	1.00	.318	-.088 .267	
OWNEC	.004	.001	3.04	.003	.002 .007	***
DETS	-.001	.002	-0.79	.43	-.005 .002	
FLAGE	-.007	.003	-2.87	.005	-.012 -.002	***
Constant	-6.802	.833	-8.17	0	-8.451 -5.153	***
R-squared		0.550	Number of obs		130	
F-test		13.127	Prob > F		0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

STATA Yields

Figure 1 Test of Unusual and Influential Data
STATA Yields

As indicated, the data is linear and therefore, best linear unbiased estimator (BLUE) can apply. We also test for normality of residual. See Table 4.

Table 4

Normal distribution check

Reside	Obsn	W	V	z	Prob > z
e	130	0.983	1.754	1.264	0.103

STATA Outputs

As shown, probability-value is insignificant, it is greater than .05. This implies that there is no problem of normality. We also test for homoscedasticity and the results are contained in Table 5.

Table 5

Cameron & Trivedi's decomposition of IM-test

Source	chi2	df	p
Heteroskedasticity	61.520	76	0.886
Skewness	20.800	11	0.035
Kurtosis	1.600	1	0.205
Total	83.920	88	0.603

STATA Outputs

As indicated by the results in Table 5, the probability value is insignificant, meaning that the data has no problem of heteroskedasticity. We also test for multicollinearity and the results are indicated in Table 6.

Table 6

Difference inflation elements

	VIF	1/VIF
FLAGE	1.651	.606
BIGFO	1.546	.647
BSIZE	1.541	.649
OWNEC	1.468	.681
BMEET	1.348	.742
BINDE	1.305	.766
BREMU	1.265	.791
DETA5	1.18	.847
BOWNE	1.127	.887
BDIVE	1.106	.904
Mean	1.369	.

VIF

STATA Outputs

Based on the results contained in Table 6, there is no evidence to support multicollinearity among the independent and control variables. We equally test for linearity and the results are contained in Figure 2a-2b. Note that the test was done for only the independent variable (board governance).

Figure 2b Linearity Test Results
STATA Outputs

A cursory look at the graphs indicate that the problem of linearity is evident but the issue is not big enough to serve as a source of worry. We also test for model specification error and the results of the two tests (linktest and ovtest) are reported in Tables 7 and 8. While the model specification error test (linktest) indicate that the model was correctly specified, the results of omitted variables test indicate that there are omitted variables. We therefore add sales growth to the model as additional control variable; yet, it was not satisfied. We then decide to drop firm size and sales growth from the equation completely and the two conditions were met. See the results of the two tests.

Table 7
Model Specification Error Test Results

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs = 130		
Model	8.835	2	4.418	Prob>F = .000		
Residual	23.388	127	0.184	R ² = .274		
Total	32.223	129	0.250	Root MSE = .429		
SUSTA	Coef.	Std.Err.	t	P>t	[95%Con	Interval]
					f.	
_hat	1.500	0.578	2.600	0.011	0.356	2.644
_hatsq	-0.424	0.474	-0.890	0.373	-1.362	0.514
_cons	-0.119	0.159	-0.750	0.458	-0.433	0.196

STATA Yields

Table 8

OV ResultsRamsey RESET test(SUSTA)

Ho: model has no omitted variables

F (3, 116) = .50

Prob > F = .6852

STATA Yields

Now, the probability values in both Tables 7 and 8 are not insignificant, meaning that there is no error in terms of model specification. We also test for panel effects and the results are contained in Table 9.

Table 9

Panel Effects Test

	Var	Sd = sqr (Var)
SUSTA	.2497913	.49979913
e	.1703568	.4127431
u	.0205153	.1432318
Var(u) = 0		
Chibar ² (01) = .64		
Prob>chibar ² = .2121		

STATA Yields

The Prob > chibar² in Table 9 is not significant, meaning that there are no panel effects in the model and therefore we do not need panel regression. We test for final regression using Probit regression.

Table 10

Probit Regression Results

SUSTA	Coef.	St.Err.	t-val.	p-val.	[95% Interval]	Sig
BFSIZE	-.022	.041	-0.52	.6	-.102 .059	
BMEET	-.021	.068	-0.31	.759	-.153 .112	
BINDE	.059	.014	4.23	0	.032 .087	***
BDIVE	-.004	.011	-0.39	.696	-.025 .017	
BOWNE	-.008	.009	-0.91	.364	-.025 .009	
BREMU	-.026	.066	-0.39	.695	-.155 .103	
BIGFO	.296	.343	0.86	.388	-.377 .969	
OWNEC	.011	.006	1.76	.078	-.001 .022	*
DETA	-.01	.005	-1.99	.047	-.019 0	**
FLAGE	.015	.009	1.66	.097	-.003 .032	*
Constant	-2.82	1.291	-2.18	.029	-5.351 -.289	**
Pseudo r-squared		0.228	Number of obs		130	
Chi ²		32.720	Prob > chi ²		0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

STATA Yields

From above, board independence, ownership concentration, leverage and listing age are the determinants of sustainability in this article while board size, meetings, diversity ownership, remuneration, big4 are not.

CONCLUSION

This paper examines the effect of board governance on the sustainability reporting of Nigeria's listed corporations. Two board conclusions are drawn from the results of the paper: board independence, ownership concentration, leverage and listing age are determinants of sustainability disclosure in Nigeria; board size, meetings, gender diversity, ownership, remuneration and big4 auditors are not determinants. This is among the few studies to examine the link between board governance and sustainability disclosure in Nigeria. However, a discussion on the role of board governance is necessary. The study calls for more studies on board governance and SD relation. This conclusion is important for shareholders and regulators to appreciate that board size, the frequency of board meetings, women on the board, equity holdings by members of the board and their remuneration have no bearing on sustainability disclosure.

REFERENCES

- Agyemang, A. O., Yusheng, K., Ayamba, E. C., Twum, A. K., Chengpeng, Z., & Shaibu, A. (2020). Impact of board characteristics on environmental disclosures for listed mining companies in China. *Environmental Science and Pollution Res.*, 27(17), 21188-21201.
- Ahmad, N.B.J., Rashid, A. & Gow, J. (2018). Corporate board gender diversity and corporate social responsibility reporting in Malaysia. *Gender, Technology and Dev.*, 22(2), 87–108.
- Al-Qahtani, M. and Elgharbawy, A. (2020). The effect of board diversity on disclosure and management of greenhouse gas information: Evidence from the United Kingdom. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 33(6), 1557–1579.
- Al-Amosh, H., & Khatib, S. F. (2021). Ownership structure and environmental, social and governance performance disclosure: the moderating role of the board independence. *Journal of Business and Socio-Economic Development*, 2(1), 49-66. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JBSED-07-2021-0094>
- Al-Shaer, H., & Zaman, M. (2019). CEO compensation and sustainability reporting assurance: Evidence from the UK. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 158(1), 233-252.
- Amran, A., Lee, S.P. & Devi, S. S. (2014). The influence of governance structure and strategic corporate social responsibility toward sustainability reporting quality. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 23(4), 217–235.
- Araissi, M., Dah, M.A. & Jizi, M. (2016). Women on boards, sustainability reporting and firm performance. *Sustainability Accounting, Mgt and Policy Journal*, 7(3), 376–401.
- Asaolu, T.O., Agboola, A.A., Ayoola, T.J. & Salamu, M. K. (2011). Sustainability in the Nigerian oil and gas sector. Environmental Management Conference Proceedings. Nigeria: Federal University of Agriculture Abeokuta.
- Asuquo, A. I. (2012). Environmental friendly policies and their financial effects on corporate

- performance of selected oil and gas companies in Niger Delta region of Nigeria. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 2(1), 1–173.
- Bae, S. M., Masud, M. A. K., & Kim, J. D. (2018). A cross-country investigation of corporate governance and corporate sustainability disclosure: A signaling theory perspective. *Sustainability*, 10(8), 2611.
- Beji, R., Yousfi, O., Loukil, N. & Omri, A. (2021). Board diversity and corporate social responsibility: Empirical evidence from France. *J. of Business Ethics*, 173(1), 133–155.
- Bektur, C., & Arzova, S. B. (2020). The effect of women managers in the board of directors of companies on the integrated reporting: Example of Istanbul stock exchange (ISE) sustainability index. *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment*, 12(2), 638–654.
- Buallay, A., Hamdan, R., Barone, E. & Hamdan, A. (2020). Increasing female participation on boards: Effects on sustainability reporting. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 18(5), 886–910.
- Chinonyelum, E. M & Ndubuisi, N. A. (2022). Effect of board structure on sustainability reporting of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management Studies and Social Science Research*.
- Cicchello, A.F., Fellegara, A.M., Kazemikhasragh, A. & Monferra, S. (2021). Gender diversity on corporate boards: How Asian and African women contribute on sustainability reporting activity. *Gender in Management: An International Journal*, 36(7), 801–820.
- Dewi, K. R. C., Rasmini, N. K., & Ratnadi, N. M. D. (2019). The Effect of Independent Board of Commissioners, Institutional Ownership, and Managerial Ownership in Firm Values with Environmental Disclosure as Moderating Variable. *International Journal of Sciences: Basic and Applied Research*, 48(2), 53-67.
- Dibia, N.O., & Onwuchekwu, J. O. (2015). Determinant of environmental disclosure in Nigeria: A case study of oil and gas companies. *International Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 4(2), 115–135.
- Dienes, D., Sassen, R., & Fischer, J. (2016). What are the drivers of sustainability reporting? A systematic review. *Sustainability Accounting, Management and Policy Journal*.
- Eberhardt-Toth, E. (2017). Who should be on a board corporate social responsibility committee? *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 140, 1926–1935.
- Ejoh, N.O., Orok, E.O. & Sackey, J. A. (2014). The development of environmental accounting and disclosure practice of manufacturing companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 5(12), 70–79.
- Enahoro, J. A. (2009). Design and bases of environmental accounting in oil and gas and manufacturing sectors in Nigeria. A PhD Thesis Submitted to the department of Accounting College of Business Administration, and Social Sciences. Ota, Nigeria: Covenant University.
- Erin, O. & Adegboye, A. (2021). Do corporate attributes impact integrated reporting quality? An empiricalevidence. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*.
- Fernandez-Feijoo, B., Romero, S. and Ruiz-Blanco, S. (2014). Women on boards: Do they affect sustainabilityreporting? *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 21(6), 351–364.

-
- Gardazi, N. S. S., Hassan, S. F. A. & Johari, B. J. (2020). Board of directors attributes and sustainability performance in the energy industry. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(12), 317–328.
- Gavana, G., Gottardo, P., & Moiselto, A. M. (2017). The effect of equity and bond issues on sustainability disclosure. Family vs non-family Italian firms. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 13(1), 126-142.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/SRJ-05-2016-0066>.
- Gerged, A. M. (2021). Factors affecting corporate environmental disclosure in emerging markets: The role of corporate governance structures. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 30(1), 609-629.
- Githaig, N. P & Kosgei, K. J. (2022). Board characteristics and sustainability reporting. A case of listed firms in East Africa. *Corporate Governance International Journal of Business in Society*.
- Githaiga, N . P & Kosgei, K. J. (2022). Board characteristics and sustainability reporting. A case of listed firms in East Africa. *Corporate Governance International Journal of Business in Society*.
- Global Reporting Initiative, G. R.I . (2021). “Consolidated set of GRI sustainability reporting standards 2020”, available at: www.globalreporting.org/how-to-use-the-gri-standards/resource-center/.
- Gul, F.A. & Leung, S. (2004). Board leadership, outside directors’ expertise and voluntary corporate disclosures. *Journal of Accounting and Public Policy*, 23(4), 351–379.
- Haladu, A & Salim, B. B. (2016). Board Characteristics and Sustainability Reporting: Environmental Agencies’ Moderating Effects. *International Journal of Economics and Financial*, 6(4), 1525–1533.
- Haniffa, R. & Cooke, T. (2000). Culture, corporate governance and disclosure in Malaysia corporations. In Asian AAA World Conference, Singapore, 20, 28–30.
- Haque, F. (2017). The effects of board characteristics and sustainable compensation policy on carbon performance of UK firms. *The British Accounting Review*, 49(3), 347-364.
- Herbohn, K., Walker, J., & Loo, H. Y. M. (2014). CSR: The link between sustainability disclosure and sustainability performance. *Abacus*, 50(4), 422-459.
- Herda, D.N., Taylor, M.E. & Winterbotham, G. (2012). The effect of board independence on the sustainability reporting practices of large US firms. *Issues in Social and Environmental Accounting*, 6(2), 178–197.
- Hu, M., & Loh, L. (2018). Board governance and sustainability disclosure: A cross-sectional study of Singapore-listed companies. *Sustainability*, 10(7), 2578.
- Jangu, T., Darus, F., Zain, M.M. & Sawani, Y. (2014). Does good corporate governance lead to better sustainability reporting? An analysis using structural equation modeling. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 145, 138–145.
- Jaturat, M., Dampitakse, K., & Kuntonbutr, C. (2021). The effect of corporate governance on the board of directors' characteristics and sustainability disclosure: An empirical study from Thailand. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(12), 191-201.
- Khairiddine, H., Salhi, B., Aljabr, J. & Jarboui, A. (2020). Impact of board characteristics on governance, environmental and ethical disclosure. *Society & Bus.*, 15(3), 273–295.

- Khan, H. U. Z. (2010). The effect of corporate governance elements on corporate social responsibility (CSR) reporting: Empirical evidence from private commercial banks of Bangladesh. *International Journal of Law and Management*, 52(2), 82–109.
- Kumar, K., Kumari, R., Poonia, A., & Kumar, R. (2021). Factors influencing corporate sustainability disclosure practices: empirical evidence from Indian National Stock Exchange. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/JFRA-01-2021-0023>
- Mahmood, Z., Kouser, R., Ali, W., Ahmad, Z., & Salman, T. (2018). Does corporate governance affect sustainability disclosure? A mixed methods study. *Sustainability*, 10(1), 207.
- Marwa, M., Salhi, B., & Jarboui, A. (2020). Environmental audit and environmental disclosure quality. *Scientific Annals of Economics and Business*, 67(1), 93-115.
- Masud, M.A.K., Nurunnabi, M. & Bae, S. M. (2018). The effects of corporate governance on environmental sustainability reporting: empirical evidence from South Asian countries. *Asian Journal of Sustainability and Social Responsibility*, 3(1), 1–26.
- Mnif, Y. & Borgi, H. (2020). The association between corporate governance mechanisms and compliance with IFRS mandatory disclosure requirements: evidence from 12 African countries, *Corporate Governance: The Int. J. of Business in Society*, 2(7), 1371–1392.
- Mock, T. J., Strohm, C., & Swartz, K. M. (2007). An examination of worldwide assured sustainability reporting. *Australian Accounting Review*, 17(41), 67-77.
- Ndaluh, C. T., Ibanichuka, L. A. E & Ofurum, O. C. (2021). Board characteristics and environmental disclosure of quoted oil and gas firms in Nigeria: The moderating role of firm size. *Int. Journal of Innovative Finance and Economics Research*, 9(4), 51–62.
- Nelson, J. & Grayson, D. (2017). World business council for sustainable development. In *Corporate Responsibility Coalitions*, Routledge, 300–317.
- Ntim, C.G. & Soobaroyen, T. (2013). Corporate governance and performance in socially responsible corporations: New empirical insights from a neo-institutional framework. *An International Review*, 21(5), 468–494.
- Nursimloo, S., Ramdhony, D. & Mooneepen, O. (2020). Influence of board characteristics on TBL reporting, Corporate Governance. *The International Journal of Business in Society*, 20(5), 765–780.
- Oba, V. C., & Fodio, M. I. (2012). Board characteristics and the quality of environmental reporting in Nigeria. *The Journal of Accounting and Management*, (2), 33-48.
- Ong, T. & Djajadikerta, H. G. (2018). Corporate governance and sustainability reporting in the Australian resources industry: an empirical analysis. *Social Responsibility Journal*, 16(1), 1–14.
- Osazuwa, N. P., Che-Ahmad, A., & Che-Adam, N. (2016). Board characteristics and environmental disclosure in Nigeria. *International Information Institute (Tokyo). Information*, 19(8A), 3069.
- Oyekale, P. J., Olaoye, S. A., & Nwaobia, A. N. (2022). Corporate Governance and Environmental Sustainability Disclosure in Non-financial Companies Quoted in Nigeria. *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 10(2), 121.
- Perego, P. (2009). Causes and consequences of choosing different assurance providers: An

international study of sustainability reporting. *International Journal of Management*, 26(3), 412-425.

- Rezaee, P. (2009). Sustainable development and the sustainability of competitive advantage: A dynamic and sustainable view of the firm. *Creativity & Innovation Management*, 11(3), 135–146.
- Shamil, M.M., Shaikh, J.M., Ho, P.L. & Krishnan, A. (2014). The influence of board characteristics on sustainability reporting: Empirical evidence from Sri Lankan firms. *Asian Review of Accounting*, 22(2), 78–97.
- Umar, M. M., Mustapha, L. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2021). Sustainability reporting and financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Advance Research in Business Management and Accounting*, 7(3), 21-32.
- Uwuigbe, U. N., Egbide, B. C., & Ayokunle, A. M. (2011). The effect of board size and board composition on firm's corporate environmental disclosure: A study of selected firms in Nigeria. *Acta Universitatis Danubius. Œconomica*, 7(5).
- Van Buskirk, A. (2012). Disclosure frequency and information asymmetry. *Review of Quantitative Finance and Accounting*, 38(4), 411–440.
- Viana, D. B. C., & Crisóstomo, V. L. (2020). The effects of voting ownership concentration on social and environmental disclosure: empirical evidence from Brazil. *Revista Brasileira de Gestão de Negócios*, 21, 906-927.
- Vitolla, F., Raimo, N. & Rubino, M. (2020). Board characteristics and integrated reporting quality: An agency theory perspective. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 27(1), 1152–1163.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Alkasim, A. (2021). Sustainability and profitability of listed insurance firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Accounting and Sustainability*, 6(1), 17-28.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Andow, H. A. (2015). Capital structure and firm's financial performance: Panel evidence of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. *Kaduna Business Management Review*, 2(1), 45-56.